

On Cosmic Religion: A Call to Action

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Abstract

In this call to action, the author discusses the presence of the Master, and the way to self-realization.

Divinities incarnate,

Long eras in our history have gone by, but there has been no uniting force in the world, no world religion, a common denominator applicable to all races, faiths and creeds.

With the experiment of the United States of America, we have seen how a founding document, "All men are created equal," can lead to abolition of racial divisions and even the election of an African-American president.

I propose that all men be united under God. All civilizations pay homage to the same deity, the Self of All. This Self is the finest conception of all great religions, and there are many.

This is not a divisive force, it is the Totality Itself. It is the Cosmos worshipping Itself, in Itself. The purpose of uniting under a common banner of Self, can hardly be overstated. It is the creed that all thinking denizens of the World abide by, that matter and energy in space and time are all-pervading, pointing to an underlying unital reality, which is the total consummate goal of all cognizing beings. Unified under this banner, we will eliminate all division in one fell swoop.

The force that can take mankind forward into this chapter of universal religion, I today introduce to you, a modern Master of India, Paramahansa Baba Prajnananandaji.

The scourge of the modern age is the instant, coffee shop nirvana promised by teachers left, right and center. But here is a Master who picks one up from wherever one may be and transforms the lower tendencies into high soul aspirations. Not mere aspirations remaining as aspirations but actual experience of the truths contained in all the scriptures of the world.

The very thought of the soul-goal brings to mind images of fiery Vivekananda, of soulful Yogananda and blissful Rama-tirtha and God-intoxicated Rumi. But where in the world would one go to fulfill such aspiration? Now by divine fiat comes the soul-ution: seek the truth at the feet of the modern day saint, the India-loving and world-gracing, supreme-knowing Paramahamsaji.

The thought of being in the presence of Paramahamsaji brings peace, extreme anticipation, as though a rendezvous with a supreme being is about to

transpire. And every small inch of expectation is fulfilled. Not that expectation is the right thing to keep but every heartfelt soul-desire materializes at the visual experience of the Master.

The one who can rekindle the soul-spirit within him, the hidden soul-idealism, can benefit greatly from the Master's glance. Spare a thought for the Master's well-being, and you are looked after. Think deeply of Truth as you comprehend it, and it indeed arises within, taking over the body-kingdom and engulfing one in an unshakable peace in His presence.

I throw you a challenge: realize the divine goal this life, this year, this day, this minute, shake off your slumber and plunge within. Then, if Master's presence is there, your soul will catch fire. It will rise and rise, like an upward comet. You will instantly be realized. The Divine will make home in your conscious experience.

Thriving on the Master's guidance, one fulfills the life purpose. The purpose of all the various lives that one has lived so far is cognized. In being cognized it is fulfilled, for Truth is of this nature. The one Goal of all human existence, all matter, all energy, is oneness with Divinity. The ocean also beckons, it is not that it is a single sided romantic affair.

Simple and straightforward, the path is known by the few who are blessed. The chosen ones will come to know the Truth of the Master, through the Master and in the Master. Realization is constant cognition and recognition of the Divine now. It is so solid, so real, that the so called tangible reality pales in comparison.

The road is long if walking alone, now with the Master's presence and positive experience, the long road becomes through and through a simple convenient reality. Not troublesome anymore, the path becomes straight as a knife's edge. The only equipment one needs is one's deep determination. Constant affirmation of this determination brings fruition to the soul's effort to be with the Master in Reality.

Simple truths are sometimes complex to understand. The simplest of all is the achievement of realization through the Master. How can a supposed human being lead another human being to discovery of soul-consciousness? The grandeur of this experiment merits some consideration.

Take a rope, leave it by itself, and it falls on the ground, coiled up or straight. However, play a little charming music with skill and the supposed rope comes alive, inching vertically upwards and upwards, interminably. This is not simply the Great Rope Trick. It is not a trick at all. This is the fact, the reality of life and its realization.

The Master is the skillful musician, the disciple is the limp rope. When the Master begins to skillfully shape the disciple, the life of the disciple takes a divine turn, an upward turn, and rises and rises with no end. It penetrates all lower spheres and soon the disciple is floating in the troposphere of realization.

He sees there that Master is in the stratosphere, or ionosphere. Only such a one as this can play the music that enlivens the flung rope-on-the-ground. When in the presence of such a one, the soul rope catches fire, like the tail of a firework rocket and flies into realization, Brahman Itself. Never think that

you cannot reach the soul goal. Given the presence of the Master, act at once to form the Divine relationship. Nurture it and leave the rest to Divinity, to Providence. Sooner or later, your life rope will shoot up, dance in the Divine presence of Master.

What an interminable joy, what cloud-like lightness of heart, what divine sat-chit-ananda. This is the grace of the Master, Gurudev Baba Prajnananandaji who graces this planet Earth, a uniting force among the petty. Take the rope, O Divine one, and light up this life. Let this be the prayer. Then it is that we shall be Vivekanandas, then it is that we shall live like Yogananda and fling the lower nature into the Mother of the Universe like Rama-tirtha.

The moment of truth for human history is here. We shall either unite under common understanding or perish with misunderstanding. That unity which we cognize, is evident today from science too. A moment's scientific analysis reveals the near-homogeneity of the human genome among races.

But science need not be a walking stick. Let direct experience alone convince the worshiper of this Universal Religion. Let each person simply be the Self and find that the Self is become All. Man will have to do this and write the next great chapter in the human story.